

Traditional and modern teaching/learning methods by using ICT instruments

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REZUMAT

În scopul dinamizării procesului de instruire, al sporirii atractivității procesului didactic, a îmbunătățirii condițiilor de predare-învățare a disciplinelor socioumane, este necesară și benefică diversificarea metodelor și tehnicilor didactice prin utilizarea instrumentelor TIC (a resurselor hardware și software). Ajustând TIC la cerințele procesului de predare-învățare, remarcăm că studenții/masteranzii devin mai receptivi la posibilitățile pe care acestea le oferă, învățând să profite de lărga gamă a informațiilor, astfel fiind înlăturate impedimentele existente.

In order to enhance the teaching process, to enrich the attractiveness of the didactic process, to improve the teaching and learning conditions of socio-humanities disciplines in the epoch of rapid change and profound interconnections, it is necessary to diversify the teaching/learning methods through the use of ICT instruments (hardware and software resources). Using the computer, the digital or analogous recording devices (including DVD and video), cameras, photocopiers, printers, as well as traditional learning strategies, such as PowerPoint, in the teaching process, undergraduate/master students become more receptive to the opportunities they provide and learn to take advantage of the large choice of information, thus removing the existing impediments in the teaching/learning process.

In this study, we will focus on the diversity of teaching/learning methods used in socio-humanities disciplines which resort to ICT instruments (such as brainstorming, starbursting, round table, heuristic conversation method, the cube method, the pyramid method, project method, case study). They contribute to the creative solution of the tasks, proposed by the teacher, and to the involvement of the students in the teaching/learning process.

The idea of a simple learning process cal-

led **brainstorming** belongs to Advertising Director Alex Osborn, which is described in his work *Applied Imagination* (1946). The aim of the author was to make the business meetings more effective. According to the author, *brainstorming* is a conference technique by means of which a group of people attempt to find a solution for a specific problem by gathering all the spontaneous ideas of the members of the group. The fact that *brainstorming* stimulates the creativity in a group is well-known. Its specificity resides in the split between the stage of generating ideas and their evaluation. The group is composed of four to seven persons, which allows a fruitful cooperation between colleagues for a period of 15 minutes. The choice of the leader and of the person responsible for the recording of the ideas is very important. All opinions, expressed during the discussions, should be considered. Subsequently, each subgroup separately examines all the mentioned earlier ideas and summarizes them in front of the entire group. Using ICT, the teacher announces the topic, which follows to be discussed, on his blog by specifying the stages of the work, creating electronic groups, which will take advantage of indirect contact, while the status and geographical barriers will not be noticed.

Application of the method

Discipline:	European Cultures and Civilizations
Topic:	Culture and Civilization of the Renaissance Era
Set objectives:	To interpret Renaissance as a type of transition culture and get aware of humanism as ideatic basis of Renaissance culture; to elucidate the characteristic features of humanist conception, evolution and science of the Renaissance era, and education in the Renaissance era.
Optimization by using ICT:	The number of participants is not limited, the atmosphere is relaxed, the emotional tensions are surpassed, each student focuses on acquiring personal feedback.

Starbursting represents another effective method in solving tasks through questions and focuses on activating the students' creativity. In the working process, we use the drawing of a five-pointed star, reserving one point for each question that would guide the undergraduate/graduate students to

make the right steps in research. Students are to use the information recommended by the professor by surfing the internet. This method helps students to enrich their knowledge of the field, to structure their presentations and, respectively to achieve the goals.

Application of the method

Discipline:	European Cultures and Civilizations
Topic:	The concept of culture: classical and contemporary interpretation
Set objectives:	To get familiarized with the genesis and evolution of the semantic concepts of culture and civilization, to get to know periods of culture evolution, to report tendencies of European culture and civilization evolution in the global context.
Optimization by using ICT:	ICT enhances the attractively of the discussion and increases its productivity, offers useful information on the discussed topic, helps the students to realize the essence and the importance of culture in the globalization era.

Roundtable is held by a limited number of people, the discussion being focused on a complex topic. The role of the moderator is notable and performed by the teacher or by a person selected from among the stu-

dents. It is important that all participants are involved in the discussion and have the possibility to express opinions on the discussed topic.

Application of the method

Discipline:	Management of International Projects and Programmes
Topic:	Definitions and acceptations of the term ,management'
Set objectives:	To clarify the main definitions, characteristics, useful principles of the term ,management'.
Optimization by using ICT:	ICT offers the possibility to identify new elements in the debate, to compare the submitted opinions using personal databases, to realize the discussed topics, to assess different styles of communication.

Heuristic conversation is a dialogue between the professor and the students focused on a complex topic. The addressed questions make the learners appeal to the knowledge they possess by discovering new things. Reproductive type questions (what? when? where?), hypothetical (but? what if? suppose that) and evaluative (why? which

is better? which is more effective?) should emerge from the discussed topic. The questions must be open-ended, increase responsiveness, activism, and the ability to accept impressions and to study easily. During the heuristic discussion, the ICT resources enable students to receive and consciously assimilate the new material.

Application of the method

Discipline:	Management of International Projects and Programmes
Topic:	Project management. Fundamental principles. Structural organization of project management.
Set objectives:	To analyse the stages typical of project management process, to get familiar with the fundamental principles of project management.
Optimization by using ICT:	The work takes place in real timeframe, the information may be taken from personal databases, the ability to communicate in written form is developed, the importance of on-line communication is realized.

The cube method involves the investigation of a topic from several perspectives. During the activity, a cube is used, on whose faces the glossemes, which will direct the discussion, **are** marked: *describe, compare, analyse, associate, apply, and argue*. Six groups are formed; each group is assigned a

concrete task. The information is edited by each group and can be viewed by all the colleagues through ICT integration. This step might facilitate the detailed study of the announced topics and develop students' creativity and intuition.

Application of the method

Discipline:	Management of International Projects and Programmes
Topic:	Typology of project life cycles
Set objectives:	To analyse the processes that overlap, are mutually interrelated and can run several times within the projects; to get familiar with the elementary life cycle of a project, the life cycle based on developmental stages, the life cycle based on prototype.
Optimization by using ICT:	ICT assist in learning the typology of project life cycles; enable the creation of diagrams, electronic maps, etc.

The Pyramid method is based on individual and group work. Thus, each student is involved in the training process. The given method consists of four phases: *introductory phase* (the teacher presents the problem), *personal activity phase* (every student, in

part, meditates on the discussed issue), *collective work phase* (presupposes discussions to elucidate the correctness of the expressed ideas), and *the conclusive phase* (presentation of solutions).

Application of the method

Discipline:	Management of International Projects and Programmes
Topic:	Essence and contents of project concept. Characteristics of projects. Types of projects.
Set objectives:	To get familiar with the main characteristics of a project, with the areas to be considered when dealing with project management.
Optimization by using ICT:	Time is selected by the learners; the activity occurs outside the classroom, the discussion has an interdisciplinary character. The possibility to view various projects on-line will help the learners to assimilate techniques for their elaboration.

Training through **project method** allows students to demonstrate their skills and knowledge in approaching topics taken from the curriculum. Initially, the professor appoints the topic, explains the objectives that are to be met, and sets the length of the activity. Subsequently, the learners are divided into groups. In this context, the use of

information technologies will assist students to collect and process materials by offering the possibility to work through multimedia tools, such as e-mail or personal websites. Finally, the assessment will highlight the students' ability to work individually and in groups.

Application of the method

Discipline:	European Cultures and Civilizations
Topic:	Cultural diversity - a challenge for contemporary world progress
Set objectives:	To become aware of the diversity of cultural models in the study of culture; the place of national culture within the framework of the world culture; the prominent role of democracy in society; to evaluate the role and importance of European Union bodies in the context of cultural diversity.
Optimization by using ICT:	Using ICT tools, learners will have the possibility to access on-line information, collect and interpret data. E-mail will become a tool that will enable to maintain indirect contact with the learners.

The **case study** method is used to analyse actual facts existing in society, regardless of the will of some persons. It is the basis of forms of study, proposed by Harvard Graduate School of Business Administration and created in 1926 in France by Andre Siegfried. Subsequently, it enjoyed a broader expansion in the higher education sectors, and then in those of education in general. From the point of view of the research purpose, based on which the choice of the case study is made, Robert E. Stake identifies three types of case studies: *intrinsic case study*, the researcher focuses on in-depth description

of the unified phenomenon, without testing the hypothesis or its general data; *the instrumental case study* conducted to clarify some theory or a more general issue; *the multiple (collective) case study*, which seeks to generalize characteristics and mechanisms. According to Donald T. Campbell, the case study can be viewed as a small step towards a big theory [3]. Based on well-structured questions, the case study method may incite heated discussions. Much information on the discussed topic could be taken from electronic resources, which would help elucidate more profoundly the discussed topic.

Application of the method

Discipline:	European Cultures and Civilizations
Topic:	Integration of the Republic of Moldova into European cultural realities
Set objectives:	To analyse Republic of Moldova's cultural relations with the European Union countries, the importance of national ethno-cultural organizations within the European Community area, to participate in European cultural programmes.
Optimization by using ICT:	ICT will be used to formulate hypotheses and enable reasoned assessment of the events related to the cultural life of the country.

In conclusion, the use of ICT tools in the didactic activity is necessary and beneficial. It helps diversify the teaching/learning methods, renders attractively to the discussions, enhances the productivity of the didac-

tic process, assists learners to get oriented in the hubbub of information provided by the Internet, contributes to creative solution of the tasks proposed by the teacher.

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